

TYOLOGICAL STAGES AND ERGOLOGICAL BASIS OF MUSICAL INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE

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ANNOTATION

The typological development and ergological basis of musical instrument performance are explained practically and theoretically.

Key words: *baroque, classicism, romanticism, impressionism, dynamics, composers, harmony.*

In the years of independence, special attention is being paid to the content of education, which is considered extremely important for the development of the young generation growing up in our country, to the aesthetic upbringing of students through national values, traditions and centuries-old musical heritage. Due to the fact that the world music culture is extremely rich in many masterpieces written at a professional level, which have a delicate, emotional content and essence, which have high aesthetic views and the history of their formation goes back to certain periods, the field of musical instrument performance has developed in almost all countries of the world, is developing.

It is worth noting that, on the basis of the progress of the musical education system, the faith, dreams and goals of our selfless young people who are serving for the development of the country will be formed, and the great people who will introduce the greatness of our country to the world will mature.

Declaring the education of the young generation and the effectiveness of education as a priority area of state policy in our country, in turn, leads to the development of perfect people with high consciousness, who can think independently, and these important goals and tasks acquire special relevance.

The advanced methods of studying the specific complexity aspects of the works written for musical instruments are large in terms of size and form, and they are important because they cover the goals and tasks based on organic connection. On the basis of the correct formation of the skill of working on works of various technical complexity in the performance of musical instruments, the ability to hear music, the quality of musical intuition, the speed of performance, duration, timbre coloration, the resounding power of dynamics, and the feeling of music in general. related elementary lessons - begin to appear in the student's performance.

Works with a complex form in terms of texture, structure, harmony, works of different genres (large form, polyphony, play, etude, concert) with a unique shape and color are of great importance because they require a musical and artistic approach. is enough.

In the book of musical books, the piano works of the composers who lived and created in the musical currents of baroque, classicism, romanticism, impressionism, which require a high level of professional performance, their structure, ergology and typological factors, and the performance technologies of artistic performance tools are covered.

In addition, information related to the life and work of the composer, who created works in genres of various technical complexity in the art of musical instrument performance, is presented on the basis of specific dates and events, and full monographic facts are cited.

It is extremely important to carry out purposeful performance training aimed at step-by-step performance of the piano instrument in connection with other musical disciplines, i.e. music history, music literature, theory, harmony, analysis of musical works, concert performance practice. In this process, musical ability is also strengthened. Ability is an individual characteristic of a person, which is considered a subjective factor of successful implementation of a certain activity.

It is important to develop hearing skills in children. Bella Bartók is one of the composers who made a significant contribution not only to the Hungarian but also to the world music culture and piano performance. The perfection related to the work is related to how precisely the nuances of the work are performed. Because these European and Eastern composers' methods of teaching works bring about the full expression of the theme of the work in the images of the musical artistic genres, the goals, emotions and temperament of the performance with its musical expressiveness.

For this reason, the composer's piano works are literally one of the masterpieces of the world piano art, and it is important that they are also recognized by the representatives of the piano field who are working and creating in our country today.

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